

Fertilizer Management to Increase Mango Yield and Export Revenue

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Abstract

This study focused on fertilizer management for the improvement of mango yield and the reduction of fertilizer costs to increase income from mango production. In the current study, 5 experimental models were arranged in RCBD. The following data were collected: 1) environmental data 2) fertilizer composition 3) chemical properties of the soil before and after experiments 4) analysis of growth data 5) yield of mangoes 6) analysis of production costs and profits. Of fertilizers tested, HOR3 had the greatest amount of total nutrients among the granular mixed fertilizers (HO). Nutrients in soil analyses showed that soil from the T4 experimental model, in which HOR3 was administered, had the highest levels of total nutrients. Furthermore, vegetative growth analysis showed the highest canopy growth rates in T4, T3, T2, T1, and T0 models, respectively. The study of the mango yield demonstrated that the mango trees from the T4 experimental model had the highest yield (80.62 ton/ha). In addition, the highest profits (10,096.19 usd/ha) were observed in the T4 model, which also had the lowest fertilizer costs (258.69 usd/ha). Altogether, our data demonstrated that HOR3 fertilizer increased the yield of mangoes and replenished soil nutrients to a greater extent than chemical fertilizer.

Keywords: granular mixed fertilizer, fertilizer management, production cost

1. Introduction

In Thailand, there is a high degree of mango cultivation. For example, a group of farmers in Wangtong and Nernmaprang Districts in Phitsanulok Province have used a systemic approach to export golden Barracuda mangoes to Japan. Mangoes export from these districts has brought the province fame and the country a large income. The mangoes are available all year and are exported as both fresh and processed products. Most farmers use a chemical fertilizer, especially 15-15-15 formula based fertilizers, for mango cultivation both in and out of seasons, with the proportion of fertilizer used increasing with the age of the mango trees. This use of fertilizer increases the cost of mango cultivation, results in soil degradation, and impacts the sustainability of crop production. Therefore, we developed granular mixed fertilizer (HO), an innovative fertilizer consisting of 16 essential nutrients for plants, effective microorganisms (EM), herb extracts, soil amendment, nutrient-rich compost powder, and bio-liquid hormone (for plant immune system boosters against pathogens, diseases and pests). The granular fertilizer particles were coated with a solute that functions to release fertilizer over time gradually. In this study, we focused on fertilizer management for the improvement of mango yield and to reduce fertilizer costs as well as increase income from mango grown for export (Intanon, 2013).

2. Material and Methods

HO production

HO that enhanced the growth of tree branches, tips, and leaves, was developed and designated as HOV. HOV was given to the trees in all experimental models. Additionally, HO that promoted blossoming and fruiting of mango trees were also developed and designed as HOR. HOR was prepared in 3 different

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concentrations which were low (HOR1), medium (HOR2) and high (HOR3). These innovative fertilizers were explicitly produced for mango trees. Essential nutrients from chemical fertilizer formulas 15-15-15 and 21-0-0 were mixed with EM, bio-liquid hormones, herb extract, soil amendment, and compost powder as shown in Table 1. The mixture was then granulated to allow for the controlled release of nutrients as previously described (Intanon et al., 2011).

HO administration

HO was developed as described by Japkaew and Intanon (2010). In this study, the fertilizer was explicitly produced for mango trees. The experiments were performed in the farmers' plots of 10 year old golden Barracuda mango trees that have already produced fruits. The plot size was 8x8 meters. Five experimental models were arranged in RCBD with 4 replicates (4 plants/model or 20 mango trees in total). Each experimental model was designed as follows. T0 (control) had no fertilizer. T1 was provided with 15-15-15 chemical fertilizer, T2 with HOV+HOR1, T3 with HOV+HOR2, and T4 with HOV+HOR3. The mango trees were fertilized 3 times: first, after pruning; second, when leaves have reached semi-maturity; third, after blossoming and producing fruit the size of a thumb. For T2, T3, and T4, 2 kg of HOV was first applied to each tree, followed by 2 kg of HOR with 1 kg of HOR (same concentration) being the last. The experiments were conducted between May 2017-May 2018 at Banmuanghom, Banklang Sub-district, Wangtong District, Phitsanulok Province. The following data were collected: 1) environmental data; 2) analysis on the fertilizer used in the experiment; 3) chemical properties of the soil before and after experiments; 4) canopy growth rate; 5) data of yield of mangoes; 6) production cost and profits. Statistical analysis was performed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with Duncan's new multiple range test (DMRT) at a confidence level of 95% (Intanon, 2013).

Table 1 Components of granular mixed fertilizer (%by weight)

Formula	1. Nutrients (%)	2. Compost Powder (%)	3. Soil Amendment (%)	4. Liquid herbal extract (%)	5. Bio-liquid Hormone (%)	6. Bio-liquid fertilizer with EM (%)	Total (%)
HOV	30	20	20	10	10	10	100
HOR1	15	15	40	15	10	5	100
HOR2	20	15	35	15	10	5	100
HOR3	35	15	20	15	10	5	100

1. The ratio of significant nutrients : secondary nutrients : micronutrients obtained from chemical fertilizer is 70% : 20% : 10% (Japkaew and Intanon , 2012)
2. Nutrient-rich compost powder (Japkaew and Intanon, 2012)
3. Soil amendment (Intanon 2013)
4. Compost of herb mixed with liquid herbal extract (Intanon 2013)
5. Bio-liquid hormones (Japkaew and Intanon, 2012)
6. Bio-liquid fertilizer with effective microorganisms (EM) (Chuaynon and Intanon P, 2011)

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Weather condition data

Weather condition data were collected between May 2017 to May 2018 at Lower Northern Region Irrigation Hydrology Center in Phitsanulok Province, and at the Thai Meteorological Department affiliated with Ministry of Digital Economy and Society. The highest and lowest average temperatures were 33.8 and 23.4 °C, respectively. The average amount of rainfall was 109.7 millimeters per month and the average relative humidity was 73.8-78.8%. The environment was normal and did not limit the growth of the mango trees (Figure 1).

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Figure 1 Weather conditions between May 2017 to May 2018

3.2 Analysis of HO fertilizers

Analysis of HO fertilizers showed the highest total amounts of N, P, and K in HOR3. HOR3 also contained the enormous total amounts of secondary nutrients, and micronutrients (Table 2).

Table 2 Analysis of fertilizers used in this study

Properties		Fertilizers				
		15-15-15	HOV	HOR1	HOR2	HOR3
Macronutrients	N%	15	2.55	2.65	2.71	2.80
	P%	15	1.44	1.62	1.75	1.85
	K%	15	10.29	10.54	10.73	10.97
	Total%	45	14.27	14.82	15.18	15.62
Secondary nutrients	Ca%	-	1.99	2.14	2.40	2.87
	Mg%	-	1.11	1.36	1.48	1.54
	S%	-	0.75	0.92	1.14	1.21
	Total%	-	3.86	4.42	5.02	5.62
Micronutrients	Fe (ppm)	-	1.35	1.79	2.35	2.46
	Cu (ppm)	-	44.47	47.33	49.66	53.72
	Zn (ppm)	-	139.73	155.28	189.62	203.17
	Mn (ppm)	-	254.06	272.36	281.78	298.55
	Bo (ppm)	-	30.33	33.55	35.85	37.52
	Total%	-	0.047	0.051	0.056	0.060
Organic matter	OM%	-	1.13	1.20	1.44	1.51
pH (1:1)		-	8.14	6.43	7.35	7.68
EC (1:5)	us/cm	-	67.31	66.25	63.44	61.12

3.3 Soil analysis

Soil analysis before experiments demonstrated that the soil was mildly alkaline with a pH of 8.53 and contained low organic matter (OM) which was 0.925%. The soil salinity level (EC 1:5) was very low (70.85 us/cm). After experiments, the experimental models using HO showed a neutral soil pH, medium-high OM level, very low soil salinity level, and increased nutrient level (Table 3).

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Table 3 Analysis of soil before and after planting

Properties		Before	After the experiment				
			T0 Control	T1 15-15-15	T2 HOR1	T3 HOR2	T4 HOR3
Macro nutrients	N%	1.05	1.20	1.50	1.53	1.65	1.76
	P%	0.38	0.42	0.45	0.49	0.58	0.74
	K%	1.14	1.25	1.36	1.46	1.74	2.21
	Total%	2.58	2.86	3.31	3.48	3.96	4.71
Secondary nutrients	Ca(ppm)	695.14	675.73	653.25	1364.44	1543.23	2184.77
	Mg(ppm)	153.14	157.71	196.23	373.27	446.45	491.45
	S(ppm)	3400	3900	4800	5800	6300	6500
	Total%	0.42	0.47	0.56	0.75	0.83	0.92
Micro nutrients	Fe(ppm)	1030	1040	1060	1180	1213	1531
	Cu(ppm)	1.02	1.12	1.14	1.96	2.90	4.75
	Zn(ppm)	39.69	49.58	52.29	67.41	76.23	112.77
	Mn(ppm)	33.54	33.82	39.80	85.22	141.94	163.23
	Bo(ppm)	0.19	0.25	0.35	1.38	2.06	3.75
	Total%	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.13	0.14	0.18
Organic matter	OM%	0.93	1.53	1.96	2.17	2.31	3.03
pH (1:1)		8.53	8.57	8.28	7.62	7.46	7.21
EC (1:5)	us/cm	70.85	70.83	70.16	67.14	63.16	62.23

3.4 Growth data

Growth data recorded every 15 days and between days 15-105 showed that canopy growth rate maximally increased in T4, followed by T3, T2, T1 and T0, respectively (Table 4).

Table 4 Analysis of canopy growth rate

Treatments	Canopy growth rate (cm)						
	Day 15	Day 30	Day 45	Day 60	Day 75	Day 90	Day 105
T0(Control)	16.75 ^c	33.00 ^b	50.50 ^b	55.00 ^b	67.00 ^b	73.00 ^b	86.50 ^b
T1(15-15-15)	30.50 ^{bc}	74.00 ^{ab}	84.00 ^{ab}	90.50 ^{ab}	99.50 ^{ab}	104.00 ^{ab}	110.00 ^{ab}
T2(HOR1)	70.50 ^{ab}	87.75 ^{ab}	96.25 ^{ab}	99.50 ^{ab}	109.75 ^{ab}	116.25 ^{ab}	124.75 ^{ab}
T3(HOR2)	49.75 ^{abc}	102.00 ^a	115.25 ^a	118.00 ^a	126.00 ^a	132.50 ^a	135.50 ^{ab}
T4(HOR3)	85.50 ^a	108.75 ^a	121.75 ^a	127.25 ^a	130.25 ^a	136.00 ^a	145.75 ^a
F-Test	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
CV%	55.59	37.04	30.32	28.68	23.77	22.69	19.23

* = Significant difference at probability level 0.05

3.5 Analysis of yield

The study of the yield of mangoes showed the highest total fruits in the T4 experimental model, followed by T3, T2 and T1, with T0 having the least: there were 78,550, 58,437, 58,318, 44,800, and 42,300 fruits/ha, respectively. Moreover, the maximum total fruit weight was found in the T4 model, followed by T3, T2, and T1, with T0 having the minimum: the mangoes weight were 80.6, 58.3, 50.4, 31.6, and 31.0 ton/ha, respectively (Table 5).

Table 5 Analysis of reproductive phase yield

Treatments	Total number of fruits (fruits/ha)	Weight (ton/ha)
T0 (Control)	42,300 ^b	31.0 ^b
T1 (15-15-15)	44,800 ^b	31.6 ^b
T2 (HOR1)	58,318 ^{ab}	50.4 ^{ab}
T3 (HOR2)	58,437 ^{ab}	58.3 ^{ab}
T4 (HOR3)	78,550 ^a	80.6 ^a
F-Test	*	*
%CV	25.5	40.95

* = Significant difference at probability level 0.05

3.6 Analysis of production costs and profits

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The study of production costs and profits showed the lowest fertilizer costs in the HO group (258.69 usd/ha). Moreover, the maximum net profit was found in the T4 model, followed by T3, T2, and T0, with T1 having the minimum. The net profits from T4, T3, T2, T0, and T1 models were 10096.19, 7248.51, 6210.92, 3751.06 and 3766.78 usd/ha, respectively (Table 6). Further analysis showed that T4 model had the highest profit as a percentage of the total production cost (1761 %), followed by T3 (1553 %), T2 (1332 %), and T0 (1108 %), with T1 (870 %) having the least (Table 7).

Table 6 Analysis of production cost and profits

Treatments	Labor, Pesticide and plant supplement cost (usd/ha)	Fertilizer cost (usd/ha)	Fruit tower bag cost (usd/ha)	Total cost (usd/ha)	Income (usd/ha)	Net profits (usd/ha)
T0 (Control)	446.15 ^a	0 ^c	224.11 ^d	340.00 ^c	4,109.27 ^d	3,769.27 ^d
T1(15-15-15)	446.15 ^a	486.34 ^a	237.19 ^d	430.77 ^d	4,181.83 ^d	3,751.06 ^d
T2(HOR1)	446.15 ^a	258.69 ^b	308.77 ^c	465.95 ^c	6,676.87 ^c	6,210.92 ^c
T3(HOR2)	446.15 ^a	258.69 ^b	309.40 ^b	466.58 ^b	7,715.09 ^b	7,248.51 ^b
T4(HOR3)	446.15 ^a	258.69 ^b	415.88 ^a	573.06 ^a	10,669.26 ^a	10,096.19 ^a
F-Test	Ns	*	*	*	*	*
CV%	0	68.2	25.5	18.4	41.0	42.7

* = Significant difference at probability level 0.05

Table 7 Profit as a percentage of the total cost

Treatments	Profit (%)
T0 (Control)	1,108
T1 (15-15-15)	870
T2 (HOR1)	1,332
T3 (HOR2)	1,553
T4 (HOR3)	1,761

Profit as a percentage of total cost = (net profit/total cost) x 100

4. Discussion

Analysis of fertilizers used in the experiments demonstrated that chemical fertilizer (15-15-15) contained the highest amounts of N, P, and K. Among HO formulas, the most significant amounts of macronutrients, secondary nutrients, and micronutrients were found in HOR3, followed by HOR2, with HOR1 having the least. All HOs contained all necessary nutrients for plants. The amounts of N, P, and K macronutrients were 2.55-2.80%, 1.44-1.85%, and 10.29-10.97%, respectively. The amounts of secondary nutrients (Ca, Mg, S) and micronutrients (Fe, Cu, Zn, Mn, Bo) were 3.86-5.62% and 0.047-0.060%, respectively. The abundant nutrients in HOs were obtained from various additive components used to produce fertilizers. The utilization of various components was essential for the development of fertilizers for mangoes that need several nutrients for growth development (Japkaew and Intanon, 2010).

Analysis of soil before experiments showed that the soil was mildly alkaline with pH of 8.53 and contained low OM which was 0.925 %. The soil salinity level (EC 1:5) was very low (70.85 us/cm). After experiments, the highest amounts of macronutrients, secondary nutrients, and micronutrients were observed in T4, followed by T3, T2, and T1, with T0 having the least. Analysis of nutrients in fertilizers showed that all HOs (T2, T3, T4 experimental models) contained all necessary nutrients. The soils that were administered with HOs had neutral pH, medium to medium-high OM, and very low soil salinity level. These data showed that the soil was optimal for plant growth due to its increased capability for absorbing Fe, Cu, Zn, and Mn (Intanon, 2013).

Records of mango tree growth, collected every 15 days starting from day 15, showed the highest canopy growth rate in T4, followed by T3, T2, and T1, with T0 model having the lowest (Figure 2). These results indicated that all 3 fertilizers of the HO group were composed of organic matter and hormones that supported mango growth. The fertilizers contained an adequate level of nitrogen that could support cell division in plants. Organic matter in these fertilizers could increase secondary nutrients and micronutrients. Furthermore, the fertilizers contained substances that facilitated nutrient balance, and plant hormones that enhanced growth rate. In agreement with our results, Chauynon and Intanon (2011) reported a higher growth rate in plants fertilized with HO, compared to plants fertilized with chemical fertilizer. The plant growth rate was increased due to nutrient balance in the fertilizers. The balance of nutrients also supported organic matter synthesis. Importantly, a continuous, sufficient supply of balanced nutrients can promote optimal plant growth.

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Figure 2 Growth rate of mango tree canopy

For mango yield, the highest total yield per plant was observed in the T4 experimental model, followed by T3, T2, and T1, with T0 having the least (Figure 3). In addition, the most significant total fruit weights were also found in the T4 model (Figure 4). HOs contained all nutrients including macronutrients, secondary nutrients, and micronutrients that are essential for plants. The adequate levels of nutrients could affect photosynthetic efficiency and the accumulation of organic matter, which could impact the numbers of fruits produced and total fruit weight. The utilization of HOs resulted in a high quality product due to the abundance of balanced nutrients in plants. A high level of chlorophyll supports photosynthesis in which carbohydrates, sugar, and consequential energy are synthesized in plants from energy in the sunlight (Japkaew and Intanon, 2010). When soil quality is improved with optimal organic matter and pH, plants can absorb more nutrients and green pigment chlorophyll could be increased. These could enhance photosynthesis and the accumulation of organic matter within plants, resulting in an increased yield. On the other hand, receiving incomplete and imbalanced nutrients from chemical fertilizer could affect the accumulation of starch and sugar, resulting in a low accumulation of organic matter and reduced yield (Intanon, 2013).

Figure 3 Analysis of yield per hectare

Figure 4 Analysis of yield weight

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Analysis of production cost and profits showed the lowest fertilizer costs in the HO group (258.69 usd/ha). Moreover, the maximum profits were found in the T4 model (10096.19 usd/ha), followed by T3 (7248.51 usd/ha), T2 (6210.92 usd/ha), and T0 (3751.06 usd/ha), with T1 (3766.78 usd/ha) having the minimum (Figure 5). Analyzing profits as a percentage of the total production cost showed the highest profit in T4 experimental (1761 %) model, followed by T3 (1553 %), T2 (1332 %) and T0 (1108 %), with T0 (870 %) having the least (Figure 6). Our data show that good fertilizer management results in increased mango production efficiency, which should encourage a reduction in the use of chemical fertilizer that is more expensive than HO, and thus will increase the competitiveness and income for farmers (Sawamichaia et al., 2012).

Figure 5 Analysis of fertilizer costs and net profits

Figure 6 Analysis of profits as a percentage of the cost

5. Conclusion

In summary, proper fertilizer management, using effective fertilizer increases plant growth rate. The maximum canopy growth rate was found in the mango trees from T4, followed by T3, T2, and T1, with the T0 model having the minimum. Taken together, our data showed that HOR3 fertilizer increased the yield of mangoes and replenished soil nutrients to a greater extent than chemical fertilizer. Mangoes have good yields, the highest of which are found in T4 (80.62 ton/ha), in which HOR3 was administered. Along with the increased yield, the HO group had lower fertilizer costs (258.69 usd/ha) than chemical fertilizer. Moreover, the maximum profit, found in T4 (10,096.19 usd/ha), was significantly different from other experimental models. The net yield derived from the use of HO fertilizer was higher than that of chemical fertilizer. Our data showed that proper fertilizer management helps to reduce fertilizer costs and increase income from mangoes produced for export.

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